

ROLE OF THE EUROPEAN LITERATURE IN THE INTERNATIONAL ARENA (SHAKESPEARE IN ENGLISH CULTURE AND WORLD LITERATURE)

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Abstract: The article is focused on the status of the European literature in contemporary international relations. The way of its studying and expansion throughout the world is shown as well.

Key words: international relations, culture, language, literature, history, historical and historical-political background, language policy.

Introduction

When considering the literature of the 20th century, it is necessary to know the history of that period. Without a brief historical background, we will not be able to understand why literature is engulfed in a particular mood, what events the author tells us about. Having learned the main events that influenced the development of history, culture, art and all of humanity as a whole, we will be able to present a complete picture of European literature of the 20th century.

Literature, both foreign and Russian, still turns to Shakespeare's legacy. This is a brilliant example of the living life of classics, its entry into the modern world. The 20th century especially often turns to Shakespeare, and in the article I will try to consider the most striking cases of discovering Shakespearean allusions in the works of other writers.

Research methodology

In the process of mastering the discipline, students will be able to navigate the historical and literary process of Europe in the 17th-18th centuries, acquire the skills of analyzing literary phenomena against the socio-cultural, historical and historical-political background. During the course, they will form an idea and systematize their knowledge of the literary and artistic systems of the period under study - Baroque, Classicism, Romanticism. They will be able to trace, using the example of texts studied in seminars, how the features of different genres manifest themselves, how the author and narrator are related in the text, how different genre and stylistic systems develop and change. Developing the skills of competent literary analysis of works of the specified era in accordance with the general scientific requirements of literary criticism and based on the historical, cultural and aesthetic features of the period, students will become familiar with the key trends, events and figures of European literature of the 17th-18th centuries, with methodological approaches to its study, with its evolution.

Analysis and results

William Shakespeare, an outstanding British playwright and poet of the 16th century. According to Ben Jonson, he was "the soul of his age", his era. Despite a collection of sonnets, several poems and epitaphs, Shakespeare is better known as a playwright. Researchers count 37 plays, however, this figure should be taken with a significant reservation, since in some plays a heterogeneity of styles was found, which indicates the collaboration of several

authors. Among the supposed co-authors of Shakespeare are the poet Thomas Middleton ("All's Well That Ends Well") and the playwright John Fletcher ("Henry VI"). Having experience in classical ancient drama and Italian drama of the Renaissance, Shakespeare created 37 plays, which were included in the list of the best world works. Shakespeare is one of the most studied writers in the world. A separate branch of philology even emerged - Shakespeare studies, the starting point of which can be considered Ben Jonson's preface to the first collected works of the playwright (folio of 1623). Voltaire was the first to lay the foundation of the cult of Shakespeare, which first swept Europe and then the entire world. Again and again, Shakespeare was interpreted in a new way, from the point of view of a new century, literary movement or researcher studying the writer's work.

Shakespeare's plays and poetry have lived for almost four centuries. But they do not just live, they actively participate in the literary life of modern creators, helping artists to understand their own problems. Those who stand in the same row with Shakespeare - Dante, Goethe, Cervantes - have survived mainly in one work. Shakespeare's work is in full demand, although not always, not in all eras they find a response completely, but each century seeks something new for itself in different areas of Shakespeare's work. And not only English literature is addressed to Shakespeare, his genius spreads to other European countries, China and the Arab world. In Russian literature, we can talk about the "Russian branch" of the Shakespearean tradition.

The Romantics were the first to discover Shakespeare. They, namely Voltaire, laid the foundation for the emergence of the cult of Shakespeare, which first covered Europe, and then other regions of the world. no matter how Voltaire fought against this cult later, calling Shakespeare "a barbarian who understood nothing of the rules of art", he failed to shake the general fascination with the English playwright.

The 19th century was called Hamlet's century, implying the doubts and reflections of the title character of "Hamlet". In the 20th century, after the world wars, literature threw off the "shackles" of the Victorian tradition. Shakespeare remains in literature, albeit implicitly, but at a deeper, subconscious level of the English tradition. Using many well-known plots and motifs, Shakespeare prepared fertile ground for subsequent generations.

Interest in Shakespeare changed over time. In the 19th century, as well as at the beginning of the 20th, "Hamlet" remains in the center of attention.

In the 20th century, Shakespeare's works become the mythological basis on which the foundation of the modern novel is built. As B. Pasternak noted: "he (Shakespeare) dissolves the temporality and mortality of a separate sign in the immortality of its general meaning." In the 20th century, quotation became widespread. In other words, in the 20th century, every word is already a quotation. Quotations cease to play the role of additional information when the author provides a link to its source. It organically enters the text and becomes an inseparable part of it. Thus, there is a well-known story about a man who, having read "Hamlet" for the first time, was disappointed: nothing special, a collection of common catchphrases and expressions.

The examples given show that not only representatives of English art turned to Shakespeare, and that the boldest interpretations of Shakespeare belong precisely to non-Englishmen. Does this speak in favor of the fact that English literature cannot claim to own the true Shakespearean tradition? This question has not yet been answered, and even those who have the right to define themselves as followers of this tradition cannot answer it.

However, researchers of the Shakespearean tradition still believe that there is a certain continuity between Shakespeare and representatives of English literature.

Perhaps one of the reasons for this similarity is the internal barrier to mastering "foreign" literature. V. Woolf noted that even an American writer who does not need translations cannot read Shakespeare "without the feeling that the Atlantic Ocean and two or three hundred years on the far shore of this ocean separate his culture from ours."

For English culture, we can say that Shakespeare is an integral, important and traditional figure, inseparable from the English tradition, language, and nature. According to the English writer Margot Heinemann, "Shakespeare is always here, deeply rooted in the culture, environment, and English education system."

Shakespeare has established himself as the creator of the literary language of his nation. His language is related to the pre-Shakespearean era, just as Pushkin's language is related to the pre-Pushkin era. "His dramatic heritage belongs to the whole world, but the language of Shakespeare's works belongs exclusively to the Anglo-Saxon tradition." Many of Shakespeare's phrases are perceived as long familiar, although the modern English reader needs clarification of many archaic words and unfamiliar grammatical constructions. "Shakespeare is like food. Both are taken for granted," N. F. Blake begins his study "The Language of Shakespeare."

The study of Shakespeare was the beginning of English literary criticism. Shakespeare became a kind of national symbol for England. As was said above, Shakespeare entered literature using many well-known motifs and plots, the language of his works is simple and at the same time bright, rich, in his work Shakespeare touched upon important themes that still find a response in the modern world. All this together creates a certain image of Shakespeare as a symbol, a prototype of English literature.

Naturally, when considering Shakespeare in the literature of the 20th century, it is necessary to give a brief historical background of that time. In the history of foreign literature, two periods are distinguished - 1910-1945 and 1945-1990, which allows us to present the literary process in dynamics and in connection with the events that determined the appearance of the era and the unique worldview of its contemporaries. The 20th century established a tragic worldview, and the key concepts were war, violence, technocratic consciousness, the crisis of humanistic ideals, environmental disaster, terrorism, and the nuclear threat. At the same time, its first decade was shrouded in optimism and full of hopes for the intensive development of science and technology. The first airplanes, the first trips to the North and South Poles, the discovery of quantum theory, advances in genetics - all this has not yet been clouded by negative consequences. However, the sphere of reason collided with madness, and the greatest scientific and technical achievements were used against man - first in the First World War, then in the Second. Civilization suffered innumerable human victims, cultural and material losses.

So, two world wars (1914-1918) and (1939-1945), revolutions, the fall of some states and the emergence of new ones - all this shook the world. But some writers and philosophers foresaw catastrophes, some kind of threat hanging over the world, and therefore, for the most part, the literature of the beginning of the century is imbued with anxious premonitions.

Thus, a specific image of the twentieth century emerges before us. Naturally, in such a context, Shakespeare's work appears in a completely different light than, for example, in the eighteenth century.

All this could not but affect people's worldview, the fate of culture, art, and the role of literature in the modern world.

In their work, writers address these problems, some in a pessimistic vein, while others, despite all the tragedies of the century, believe in its revival.

Several main themes of the literature of the twentieth century can be distinguished:

- The theme of war and socio-political catastrophes;
- The theme of the tragedy of the individual, striving for free self-realization and subjected to violence;
- The search for justice and the loss of spiritual harmony;
- The problem of faith and unbelief;
- The relationship between the personal and the collective, morality and politics.

In connection with all this, great changes are taking place in literature. The goal of art is changing - not to change the world, but to explore it, not to reflect it, but to reveal its essence. The artistic language changes:

- The principle of authenticity disappears;
- All sorts of deformations occur, conventionality is widely used);
- Literature organically merges with philosophy (Freudianism and existentialism).

Conclusion

When considering Shakespeare in the literature of the 20th century, it is necessary to give a brief historical background for a better understanding of the literature of that century. When conducting a lesson on the topic "Shakespeare in European Literature of the 20th Century", if there is enough time, you can remember how Shakespeare was interpreted in other centuries. Unfortunately, many wonderful works of literature are not included in the list of required reading at school. The teacher should try to include as much information as possible in his lesson, make it more rich and vivid. It is wonderful if the school has a literature club as an addition to the main subject.

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